

Notes

Studies on the Actions of Thionyl Chloride and Acetyl Chloride on Cr(VI) Oxide and Synthesis of Different Oxochloro Complexes of Quinquevalent Chromium

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ALTHOUGH chemistry of quinquevalent chromium has been the subject of immense interest in recent times, no significant progress has been made mainly due to the disproportionation in aqueous phase,

Cr in +5 oxidation state has so far been stabilised mainly in the environment of halide ions as the salts of the species $[\text{CrOX}_3]^-$ and $[\text{CrOX}_3]^{2-}$ ($X=\text{Cl}, \text{F}$), as well as in the form of nonelectrolyte, CrOX_3 and the stable adducts of CrOX_3 with organic bases. Preparation of these compounds generally involves the reduction of Cr(VI) compounds with hydrogen peroxide, halogen hydracids and alcohols¹⁻³. Besides this, there are reports on the applications of acid halides, both inorganic and organic, for the preparation of oxohalo complexes of Cr(V)^{4,5}. We have attempted here for the first time to use thionyl chloride and acetyl chloride as reductant for chromium(VI) oxide and isolated several oxochloro species by using some organic ligands such as pyridine (py), 2-cyanopyridine (Cpy), 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen). Thus, reflux of CrO_3 with thionyl chloride followed by addition of organic bases yielded nonelectrolytic compounds, CrOCl_3L ($L=\text{bipy}$ or phen) and treatment of CrO_3 with acetyl chloride under cold condition in presence of organic bases dissolved in glacial acetic acid produced salts, $\text{LH}[\text{CrOCl}_4]$ ($L=\text{py}$,

bipy or phen) as well as nonelectrolyte, CrOCl_3Cpy . All these isolated compounds were characterised by analytical data as well as by physico-chemical measurements such as magnetic susceptibility, conductivity and electronic, ir and esr spectra.

Experimental

All reagents used were of B.D.H., A. R. grade. Chromium was estimated iodometrically after conversion to chromate by Na_2O_2 oxidation. Chloride was estimated gravimetrically as AgCl . Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method. Oxidation states of chromium were estimated iodometrically.

Preparation of the complexes :

The salts $\text{LH}[\text{CrOCl}_4]$ ($L=\text{py}$, bipy or phen) : CrO_3 (1.5 g) was dissolved in small portion with stirring in ice cold acetyl chloride solution (30 ml) in a round bottom flask. To the resulting red solution, the ligand (2 ml py, 1.0 g bipy or phen) dissolved in glacial acetic acid was added gradually under ice cold condition. The red coloured compound which crystallised out was filtered, washed with glacial acetic acid and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH.

The nonelectrolyte $[\text{CrOCl}_3\text{Cpy}]$: This was prepared following the same method.

The nonelectrolytes $[\text{CrOCl}_3\text{L}]$ ($L = \text{bipy}$ or phen) : CrO_3 (1.5 g) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (25 ml) for 0.5 hr and the resultant red liquid was filtered through gooch. It was cooled in ice cold water and the ligand (1.0 g) dissolved in acetonitrile was added to this with stirring. The orange red product was filtered, washed with acetonitrile and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH.

The preparation and analytical data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 PREPARATION AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compound	Colour	Reagents	Solvent	Yield %	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			Oxidation state of chromium
					Cr	N	Cl	
$\text{PyH}[\text{CrOCl}_4]$	Brownish red	1.5 g CrO_3 + 2 ml py	Acetyl chloride	45	17.75 (17.93)	47.95 (48.73)	4.68 (4.88)	5.01
$\text{BipyH}[\text{CrOCl}_4]$	Bright red	1.5 g CrO_3 + 1.0 g bipy	"	30	14.16 (14.17)	38.28 (38.51)	7.52 (7.63)	4.98
$\text{PhenH}[\text{CrOCl}_4]$	Bright red	1.5 g CrO_3 + 1.0 g phen	"	30	13.35 (13.29)	36.10 (36.15)	6.98 (7.16)	5.03
$[\text{CrOCl}_3\text{Cpy}]$	Shinning red	1.5 g CrO_3 + 2 ml Cpy	"	30	18.54 (18.67)	37.52 (38.23)	9.79 (10.06)	4.95
$[\text{CrOCl}_3\text{.bipy}]$	Orange red	1.5 g CrO_3 + 1 g bipy	Thionyl chloride	35	15.48 (15.73)	32.52 (32.75)	8.30 (8.47)	4.90
$[\text{CrOCl}_3\text{.phen}]$	Orange red	1.5 g CrO_3 + 1 g phen	"	35	14.40 (14.67)	29.87 (30.04)	7.76 (7.90)	4.92

Results and Discussion

Conductivities of all the compounds were measured in acetonitrile using a 'Dip' type cell and values of molar conductances were calculated. The values for the salts $LH[CrOCl_4]$ are incompatible with the values of 1 : 1 electrolyte and those for the compounds $[CrOCl_4.L]$ are sufficiently low for them to be considered as nonelectrolytes⁶.

Magnetic susceptibilities of solid compounds were measured in Gouy balance at room temperature and magnetic moments in Bohr Magneton were calculated after necessary diamagnetic correction using the expression $\mu_{eff} = 2.84 (x_M' \times T)^{1/2} (x_M' = \text{corrected molar susceptibility})$. The values are found to be corresponding to the d^1 configuration with slight deviation from spin only values expected for one unpaired electron.

TABLE 2

Compound	Molar conductance (mho cm ²)	Magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) B.M.	$\nu_{Cr=O}$ cm ⁻¹	$\langle g \rangle$ Values
PyH[CrOCl ₄]	135.0	1.76 (303)	950	1.98
BipyH[CrOCl ₄]	166.15	1.85 (299)	955	1.95
PhenH[CrOCl ₄]	128.57	1.90 (299)	948	1.97
[CrOCl ₄ .bipy]	44.51	1.67 (302)	950	2.02
[CrOCl ₄ .phen]	31.77	1.71 (301)	945	2.03
[CrOCl ₄ .Cpy]	28.70	1.80 (303)	940	1.96

Values in parenthesis are the temperatures at which magnetic susceptibilities were measured.

TABLE 3

Compound	Wave length nm	Frequency kK	Molar extinction ϵ	Assignments
PyH[CrOCl ₄]	770	12.95	137.50	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	550	18.18	262.5	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	425	23.50	725.0	³ B ₂ → ³ A ₁
	390	25.64	787.50	(xy → z ²)
	305	32.78	12,500	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	240	41.67	10,200	³ B ₂ → ³ E (II)
BipyH[CrOCl ₄]	715	13.98	130	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (II)
	620	16.13	165	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	430	23.26	1060	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₁
	380	26.30	950	³ B ₂ → ³ A ₁
	295	33.90	17,300	(xy → z ²)
	232	43.10	18,250	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
PhenH[CrOCl ₄]	720	13.89	104.50	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
	510	19.61	354.50	(transition in bipyH ⁺)
	445	22.60	758	³ B ₂ → ³ E (II)
	370	27.03	545	³ B ₂ → ³ E (I)
	310	32.25	9030	³ B ₂ → ³ B ₂ (I)
	262	38.17	11,344	³ B ₂ → ³ E (II)
	262	38.17	11,344	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
[CrOCl ₄ .bipy]	720	13.98	145.0	(transition in phenH ⁺)
	630	15.58	182.64	a ₂ → b ₁ [*]
	460	21.74	416.55	a ₂ → b ₂ [*]
	400	25.00	1822	a ₂ (xy) → a ₁ [*] (x ² - y ²)
	285	35.05	14,507	a ₂ → a ₁ [*] (z ²)
	242	31.32	12,563	b ₂ → a ₁ [*]
[CrOCl ₄ .phen]	680	14.71	132.0	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
	540	18.52	461.20	(in bipy)
	415	24.10	795.36	a ₂ → b ₁ [*]
	330	30.30	7275	a ₂ → b ₂ [*]
	250	40.0	12,534	a ₂ → a ₁ [*] xy → (x ² - y ²)
[CrOCl ₄ .Cpy]	750	13.33	50.0	b ₂ → a ₁ [*] z ²
	600	16.69	148.80	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
	450	22.22	421.40	(in phen)
	395	25.31	562.0	a ₂ → b ₁ [*]
	310	32.25	5082	a ₂ → b ₂ [*]
	250	40.0	8677	b ₂ → b ₁ [*]

The infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded in Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr phase so as to locate mainly the Cr=O stretching band. The frequencies for this band, which center round 940-955 cm^{-1} are in accordance with the previous observations⁷ in similar cases.

The esr spectra of the powdered compounds were recorded on Varian V-4502 ESR spectrophotometer using X-band (9.3 GHz) r. f. field and the average $\langle g \rangle$ values were calculated. These were found to be in accordance with the low symmetry distorted octahedral field⁸ caused by the interaction of strong Cr-O multiple bond and are supported by oxidation states and values of magnetic moments. The values of molar conductance, magnetic moments, frequencies of Cr=O stretching bands and the average $\langle g \rangle$ values are given in Table 2.

The electronic spectra of the compounds were taken on Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer in acetonitrile and the bands along with the assignments on the basis of previous reports⁹⁻¹⁰ on similar compounds are given in Table 3.

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Thermodynamic Parameters of Dialkyltin(IV)-N-Arylhydroxamic Acid Chelates

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ALTHOUGH the chemistry of dialkyltin(IV) in non-aqueous media has received wide attention, information about the stability of the complexes in solution is rather meagre^{1,2}. The present work describes for the first time the thermodynamic

functions of some chelates formed by N-arylhydroxamic acids (N-phenylbenzhydroxamic, N-p-tolylbenzhydroxamic acids) with dialkyltin(IV) ions [dimethyl-, di-n-propyl- and di-n-butyltin(IV) dichlorides]. The stability constants were computed in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at 20, 30 and 40° by Calvin-Bjerrum technique^{3,4} as adapted by Rossotti and Irving⁵ employing different computational methods viz., \bar{n} and pL plot, correction term and least square methods. Thermodynamic quantities, ΔG , ΔH , ΔS and ΔCp , were calculated for the following equilibrium using the $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ data.

(R' = C₆H₅, p-C₆H₄CH₃; R = CH₃, n-C₂H₇ and n-C₄H₉)

Experimental

Dialkyltin(IV) dichlorides were distilled before use. Dioxane was dried and purified by standard methods. Double distilled water was used throughout the experiments. The chelating agents, N-arylhydroxamic acids, were synthesized by the reported methods^{6,7}. For the determination of dissociation constants^{8,9}, a solution of 0.01 M hydroxamic acid and 0.1 M NaCl in 75% dioxane-water (v/v) was titrated against 0.5 M NaOH solution at 20, 30 and 40°. Potentiometric studies were carried out on a digital pH meter (model pH 5651) of ECIL, India. All measurements were taken in nitrogen atmosphere with constant stirring magnetically. Since complexation⁸ of Cl⁻ with dialkyltin(IV) ion is negligible, metal chlorides were used for obtaining formation constant data. To avoid hydrolysis of dialkyltin ions, the present studies were carried out in dioxane-water media^{6,7}.

A solution containing 0.01 M hydroxamic acid, 0.0025 M dialkyltin(IV) dichloride and 0.1 M NaCl was titrated against 0.1 M NaOH for obtaining formation constants. Correction factors¹⁰ ($\log \mu H = 0.08$ at 20°, 0.13 at 30° and 0.17 at 40°) were applied to the observed pH values to obtain the correct pH in dioxane-water media. The average number of the ligand bound per metal ion (\bar{n}) and the free ligand concentration (L) were calculated by the literature procedure^{6,7}. The stepwise formation constants $\log q_1$ and $\log q_2$ were directly read from n, pL plot and were also computed by the least square and the correction term methods. The first, second and overall formation constants determined during the present investigation are given in Table 1. The change in free energy ($-\Delta G$) was calculated from the equation $-\Delta G = 2.303 RT \log \beta$, where R = gas constant, T = absolute temperature and $\log \beta$ = overall stability constant. The other thermodynamic functions (ΔH , ΔS and ΔCp) were calculated by plotting¹¹ the $\log \beta$ (stoichiometric or thermodynamic stability constant) vs T^{-1} . ΔH was calculated from the slope and ΔS from the intercept data.